

Laboratory for Food Safety

EURL Lm

European Union Reference Laboratory for
Listeria monocytogenes
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Set of strains of *Listeria monocytogenes* characterised by their μ_{\max} under different broth conditions

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Table of contents

Table of contents.....	2
Introduction	3
1 Strains isolated from meat products.....	4
2 Strains isolated from sea food.....	6
3 Strains isolated from dairy products.....	8
4 Strains isolated from environment	10
5 Strains isolated from vegetables	12
6 References	13
7 Annex I. Summary table of the set of strains.....	14

Introduction

The EURL *Lm* constituted a set of strains from various origin (meat, dairy products, sea food, environmental and vegetables) and various molecular serotypes. Strains were initially selected for their ability to grow rapidly and to grow in harsh conditions of temperature, pH and a_w (Guillier et al., 2013).

According to the EURL *Lm* Technical Guidance Document on challenge tests and durability studies for assessing shelf-life of ready-to-eat foods related to *Listeria monocytogenes* (EURL *Lm*, 2021), this set of strains is recommended to perform challenge tests.

In this new version, two strains have been excluded from the dataset due to their high similarity in both genomic features and growth characteristics.

Additionally, genomic data has been integrated into this updated version of the report. More information is available in (EURL *Lm*, 2025). The genomes of the strains are publicly available and accessible through the European Nucleotide Archive under the project number [PRJEB88973](#).

1 Strains isolated from meat products

Strain reference: 12MOB045LM		Isolated from: Pork carcass	
Molecular serotype: IIc		ENA Accession number: ERR14894978	
Clonal complex: CC9			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,092±0,000	0,184±0,010	0,137±0,170

Strain reference: 12MOB046LM		Isolated from: Minced beef	
Molecular serotype: IIa		ENA Accession number: ERR14894979	
Clonal complex: CC31			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,089±0,000	0,176±0,010	0,132±0,090

Strain reference: 12MOB085LM		Isolated from: Paté	
Molecular serotype: IVb		ENA Accession number: ERR14894987	
Clonal complex: CC2			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,090±0,003	0,139±0,008	0,137±0,129

Strain reference: 12MOB089LM		Isolated from: Smoked pork breast	
Molecular serotype: IVb		ENA Accession number: ERR14894988	
Clonal complex: CC2			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,092±0,004	0,194±0,004	0,126±0,119

Strain reference: 12MOB112LM		Isolated from: Pork rillettes	
Molecular serotype: IVb		ENA Accession number: ERR14895000	
Clonal complex: CC2			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,089±0,003	0,151±0,016	0,115±0,107

2 Strains isolated from sea food

Strain reference: 12MOB099LM		Isolated from: Swordfish	
Molecular serotype: IIb			
Clonal complex: CC59		ENA Accession number: ERR14894991	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,094±0,001	0,147±0,012	0,124±0,118

Strain reference: 12MOB100LM		Isolated from: Trout	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC155		ENA Accession number: ERR14894992	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,088±0,001	0,160±0,031	0,136±0,213

Strain reference: 12MOB101LM		Isolated from: Herring	
Molecular serotype: IIb			
Clonal complex: CC5		ENA Accession number: ERR14894993	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,092±0,003	0,168±0,010	0,150±0,188

Strain reference: 12MOB102LM		Isolated from: Salmon	
Molecular serotype: IVb			
Clonal complex: CC2		ENA Accession number: ERR14894994	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,092±0,001	0,161±0,012	0,135±0,170

Strain reference: 12MOB103LM		Isolated from: Panga	
Molecular serotype: IVb		ENA Accession number: ERR14894995	
Clonal complex: CC2			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,090±0,001	0,165±0,006	0,169±0,216

Strain reference: 12MOB104LM		Isolated from: Hake filet	
Molecular serotype: IIa		ENA Accession number: ERR14894996	
Clonal complex: CC31			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,089±0,005	0,175±0,007	0,119±0,080

Strain reference: 12MOB107LM		Isolated from: Trout	
Molecular serotype: IVb		ENA Accession number: ERR14894999	
Clonal complex: CC6			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,090±0,002	0,152±0,011	0,114±0,109

3 Strains isolated from dairy products

Strain reference: 12MOB053LM		Isolated from: Cheese	
Molecular serotype: IIb			
Clonal complex: CC5		ENA Accession number: ERR14894985	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ _{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,088±0,003	0,172±0,018	0,153±0,145

Strain reference: 12MOB079LM		Isolated from: Cheese	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC14		ENA Accession number: ERR14894986	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ _{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,093±0,001	0,163±0,017	0,121±0,120

Strain reference: 12MOB096LM		Isolated from: Raw sheep milk	
Molecular serotype: IVb			
Clonal complex: CC4		ENA Accession number: ERR14894989	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ _{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,096±0,002	0,174±0,009	0,137±0,172

Strain reference: 12MOB098LM		Isolated from: Cheese	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC412		ENA Accession number: ERR14894990	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ _{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,094±0,002	0,174±0,006	0,129±0,154

Strain reference: 12MOB105LM		Isolated from: Sheep cheese	
Molecular serotype: IVb			
Clonal complex: CC4		ENA Accession number: ERR14894997	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,094±0,003	0,168±0,016	0,133±0,132

Strain reference: 12MOB106LM		Isolated from: Cheese	
Molecular serotype: IVb			
Clonal complex: CC54		ENA Accession number: ERR14894998	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,093±0,002	0,161±0,007	0,140±0,178

Strain reference: 12MOB118LM		Isolated from: Goat cheese	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC26		ENA Accession number: ERR14895001	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,093±0,007	0,173±0,025	0,132±0,123

4 Strains isolated from environment

Strain reference: 12MOB047LM		Isolated from: Industrial environment	
Molecular serotype: IIb			
Clonal complex: CC3		ENA Accession number: ERR14894980	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,089±0,000	0,184±0,010	0,123±0,119

Strain reference: 12MOB048LM		Isolated from: Industrial environment	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC121		ENA Accession number: ERR14894981	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,089±0,000	0,167±0,006	0,138±0,133

Strain reference: 12MOB049LM		Isolated from: Industrial environment	
Molecular serotype: IIb			
Clonal complex: CC3		ENA Accession number: ERR14894982	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,090±0,001	0,170±0,010	0,113±0,108

Strain reference: 12MOB050LM		Isolated from: Industrial environment	
Molecular serotype: IVb			
Clonal complex: CC2		ENA Accession number: ERR14894983	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,090±0,001	0,156±0,019	0,134±0,206

Strain reference: 12MOB052LM		Isolated from: Industrial environment	
Molecular serotype: IVb		ENA Accession number: ERR14894984	
Clonal complex: CC2			
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a_w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{max} (h ⁻¹)	0,091±0,001	0,135±0,000	0,131±0,243

5 Strains isolated from vegetables

Strain reference: 20SEL274LM		Isolated from: Salad	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC18		ENA Accession number: ERR14895004	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,092±0,002	0,248±0,002	0,190±0,007

Strain reference: 20SEL17LM		Isolated from: Cantaloupe	
Molecular serotype: IIc			
Clonal complex: CC9		ENA Accession number: ERR14895003	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,088±0,004	0,270±0,013	0,173±0,014

Strain reference: 15SEL517LM		Isolated from: Frozen green asparagus	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC8		ENA Accession number: ERR14895002	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,092±0,004	0,239±0,006	0,183±0,004

Strain reference: 12CEB28LM		Isolated from: Sprouted soy	
Molecular serotype: IIa			
Clonal complex: CC31		ENA Accession number: ERR14894977	
Growth characteristics in BHI (brain heart infusion)			
Growth condition	8°C - pH 7- a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0,98	20°C- pH 7- a_w 0,95
Maximum growth rate μ_{\max} (h ⁻¹)	0,089±0,004	0,185±0,004	0,188±0,007

6 References

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7 Annex I. Summary table of the set of strains

Strain reference	Molecular serotype	CC	Origin	Isolated from	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0.98		20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0.98		20°C - pH 7 - a _w 0.95		Accession number
12MOB045LM	IIc	CC9	Meat products	Pork carcass	0,092	±0,000	0,184	±0,010	0,137	±0,170	ERR14894978
12MOB046LM	IIa	CC31	Meat products	Minced beef	0,089	±0,000	0,176	±0,010	0,132	±0,090	ERR14894979
12MOB085LM	IVb	CC2	Meat products	Paté	0,090	±0,003	0,139	±0,008	0,137	±0,129	ERR14894987
12MOB089LM	IVb	CC2	Meat products	Smoked pork breast	0,092	±0,004	0,194	±0,004	0,126	±0,119	ERR14894988
12MOB112LM	IVb	CC2	Meat products	Pork rillettes	0,089	±0,003	0,151	±0,016	0,115	±0,107	ERR14895000
12MOB099LM	IIb	CC59	Sea food products	Swordfish	0,094	±0,001	0,147	±0,012	0,124	±0,118	ERR14894991
12MOB100LM	IIa	CC155	Sea food products	Trout	0,088	±0,001	0,160	±0,031	0,136	±0,213	ERR14894992
12MOB101LM	IIb	CC5	Sea food products	Herring	0,092	±0,003	0,168	±0,010	0,150	±0,188	ERR14894993
12MOB102LM	IVb	CC2	Sea food products	Salmon	0,092	±0,001	0,161	±0,012	0,135	±0,170	ERR14894994

Strain reference	Molecular serotype	CC	Origin	Isolated from	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0.98		20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0.98		20°C - pH 7 - a _w 0.95		Accession number
12MOB103LM	IVb	CC2	Sea food products	Panga	0,090	±0,001	0,165	±0,006	0,169	±0,216	ERR14894995
12MOB104LM	IIa	CC31	Sea food products	Hake filet	0,089	±0,005	0,175	±0,007	0,119	±0,080	ERR14894996
12MOB107LM	IVb	CC6	Sea food products	Trout	0,090	±0,002	0,152	±0,011	0,114	±0,109	ERR14894999
12MOB053LM	IIb	CC5	Dairy products	Cheese	0,088	±0,003	0,172	±0,018	0,153	±0,145	ERR14894985
12MOB079LM	IIa	CC14	Dairy products	Cheese	0,093	±0,001	0,163	±0,017	0,121	±0,120	ERR14894986
12MOB096LM	IVb	CC4	Dairy products	Raw sheep milk	0,096	±0,002	0,174	±0,009	0,137	±0,172	ERR14894989
12MOB098LM	IIa	CC412	Dairy products	Cheese	0,094	±0,002	0,174	±0,006	0,129	±0,154	ERR14894990
12MOB105LM	IVb	CC4	Dairy products	Sheep cheese	0,094	±0,003	0,168	±0,016	0,133	±0,132	ERR14894997
12MOB106LM	IVb	CC54	Dairy products	Cheese	0,093	±0,002	0,161	±0,007	0,140	±0,178	ERR14894998

Strain reference	Molecular serotype	CC	Origin	Isolated from	8°C - pH 7 - a _w 0.98		20°C- pH 5 - a _w 0.98		20°C - pH 7 - a _w 0.95		Accession number
12MOB118LM	Ila	CC26	Dairy products	Goat cheese	0,093	±0,007	0,173	±0,025	0,132	±0,123	ERR14895001
12MOB047LM	Ilb	CC3	Environment	Industrial environment	0,089	±0,000	0,184	±0,010	0,123	±0,119	ERR14894980
12MOB048LM	Ila	CC121	Environment	Industrial environment	0,089	±0,000	0,167	±0,006	0,138	±0,133	ERR14894981
12MOB049LM	Ilb	CC3	Environment	Industrial environment	0,090	±0,001	0,170	±0,010	0,113	±0,108	ERR14894982
12MOB050LM	IVb	CC2	Environment	Industrial environment	0,090	±0,001	0,156	±0,019	0,134	±0,206	ERR14894983
12MOB052LM	IVb	CC2	Environment	Industrial environment	0,091	±0,001	0,135	±0,000	0,131	±0,243	ERR14894984
20SEL274LM	Ila	CC18	Vegetables	Salad	0,092	±0,002	0,248	±0,002	0,190	±0,007	ERR14895004
20SEL17LM	Ilc	CC9	Vegetables	Cantaloupe	0,088	±0,004	0,270	±0,013	0,173	±0,014	ERR14895003
15SEL517LM	Ila	CC8	Vegetables	Frozen green asparagus	0,092	±0,004	0,239	±0,006	0,183	±0,004	ERR14895002
12CEB28LM	Ila	CC31	Vegetables	Sprouted soy	0,089	±0,004	0,185	±0,004	0,188	±0,007	ERR14894977